

On the scan zero point convention (Ω)

L Lindegren (1982 March 13)

In a previous note (1981 Feb 6, "Suggestions for simulation of set solutions") I proposed using the "set-related attitude angles",

$$(u, v, \omega^*) \quad (1)$$

for the attitude simulation, rather than the usual attitude angles,

$$(\alpha_z, \delta_z, \omega). \quad (2)$$

[N.B.: the ω in (1) is not the same as in (2); the former is here denoted ω^* . This distinction was unfortunately not made in the earlier note.]

The reason for this artifice was to have a set of orthogonal (Eulerian-like) angles for which it would be reasonable to assume independent random motions. In order to retain the original definition of origin on the PGC, viz. its intersection with the equator, I propose here to simulate the attitude motion in the usual attitude angles, (2), by taking into account the coupling between these angles.

Thus consider the three orthogonal axes $\underline{u}$, $\underline{v}$, $\underline{z}$:

$$\underline{u} = \underline{x} \cos \omega - \underline{y} \sin \omega$$

$$\underline{v} = \underline{x} \sin \omega + \underline{y} \cos \omega \quad (3)$$

$$\underline{z} = \underline{z}$$

with $\underline{u}$ towards the PGC origin (at the equator) and $\underline{v}$ 90° ahead on the PGC. The differential rotations about these axes, given small changes in the attitude angles (2), are:

$$\Delta u = \Delta \delta_z$$

$$\Delta v = \Delta \alpha_z \cos \delta_z \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta \omega^* = \Delta \alpha_z \sin \delta_z + \Delta \omega$$

Now the variation (during a set) of Δu , Δv , $\Delta \omega^*$ is simulated exactly as described in the previous note, i.e. as a linear law plus Markov process; then we convert these into

$$\Delta \delta_z = \Delta u$$

$$\Delta \alpha_z = \Delta v / \cos \delta_z \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta \omega = \Delta \omega^* - \Delta \alpha_z \sin \delta_z$$

and add them to the mean attitude angles of the set. The field coordinates (η, ζ) are then computed by means of the usual rigorous formulae,

$$\sin \zeta = \sin \delta_z \sin \delta + \cos \delta_z \cos \delta \cos(\alpha - \alpha_z) \quad \Rightarrow \quad \zeta \quad (6)$$

$$\cos \zeta \cos q_z = \sin \delta \cos \delta_z - \sin \delta_z \cos \delta \cos(\alpha - \alpha_z) \quad (7)$$

$$\cos \zeta \sin q_z = \cos \delta \sin(\alpha - \alpha_z) \quad (8)$$

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2}\pi - q_z - \omega \mp \frac{1}{2}\gamma \quad (9)$$